

An introduction to the use & misuse of climate change data for climate services

Figure 1: climate simulations – 1960s computing to the ecology & people affected today (DALL-E 3)

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Summary

This report provides a concise introduction to the sources of, and examples of, tensions in using climate model projection data for climate services. These tensions arise from five interrelated sources: the original scientific purpose of global climate modelling, determining the accuracy of projection data, the ability to model the impacts of climate change, the presentation and contextualization of data to inform users, and the responsibility of data and service providers to ensure societal equity and accessibility, which in turn requires ongoing funding.

The report begins with a historical perspective, including the aspirations of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) and the United Nations (UN) regarding the importance of communicating impacts and user-centric needs for climate change information. The current state of climate services is then described, incorporating critiques from the literature, which highlight the need for co-production, effective communication of confidence, and the notion that the knowledge required for society to respond to climate change should be considered a public good.

Some fundamentals of climate modelling are discussed, specifically focusing on uncertainty and the representation of extremes. Three real-life examples from recent papers illustrate the practicalities of using models and data, and their translation into services: the first example addresses model selection from CMIP6, the second deals with deep uncertainty related to sea level rise, and the third examines the challenge of resolution as a pivotal point in derived products. To expand on practical data use, the report also briefly describes decision support tools, which are common outputs of research projects and provide controlled ways for users to interact with data.

Finally, the report reflects on current views of the future of climate modelling, including the potential for Earth System Modelling to achieve global kilometre-scale modelling and whether more qualitative or narrative descriptions could be more usable for climate services and adaptation.

1. Introduction

Climate services provide climate information to assist decision-making, based on credible information and meeting users' needs to reduce the impact of climate related hazards and increase benefits from benign climate conditions (Hewitt et al., 2012). Climate services are maturing but tensions persist which are the basis for the use and misuse of the climate modelling and data on which the services are founded. Some tensions are a product of history – based on the relationship between weather and climate modelling and the service providers, some fundamental to climate models and some part of social, economic, or political influences.

The following five interwoven data issues set the context for this report, and at any one time are interchangeably the overt topic or elephants in the room.

- i. **Purpose:** climate model projections were originally for the scientific understanding of the global climate system and to provide evidence for the need for greenhouse gas mitigation (Nissan et al., 2019). The needs of climate services are mostly on finer temporal and spatial scales, including the potential for low-likelihood, high impact extremes. Additionally, weather, climate and climate change can be conflated, and the needs of a climate service user may be outside climate projections, for example, seasonal forecast products. Climate services therefore may be guidance on preparing for a warmer world at end of century, or they may include nearer-term forecasts.
- ii. **Accuracy:** weather models can be verified against observations, thereby determining skill. At climate projection timescales the approach is to characterise uncertainty instead which varies by scale, variable/phenomenon of interest, and model version. Reducing uncertainty is an aim of science but accuracy may not be paramount, and climate services have been critiqued for focusing on better data rather than improving usability (Findlater et al., 2021).
- iii. **Impacts:** do projections underestimate or overestimate impacts? Underestimates stem from CMIP members based on availability rather than maximising a plausible spread, and themselves are families of models with interdependencies so there could be common limitations and biases (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 108). Outlier models are rarely discussed (Nissan et al., 2019), deep uncertainty and compounding risks are not included (Rising et al., 2022). On overestimates, emission scenarios have been criticised as conflating exploratory and policy relevant pathways, e.g., RCP8.5 was an inadvertent bias (Hulme, 2023) as unrealistically high encouraging 'the scientific literature to become unbalanced in an apocalyptic direction' (Pielke & Ritchie, 2021).
- iv. **Users:** climate services have been persistently characterised as requiring user-provider partnerships and co-production (Hewitt et al., 2012; Vaughan & Dessai, 2014). The benefits of user-centric information and services is indisputable. Caveats include that it requires engaged users, that there are limits to how much contextualising of data a user may absorb and that co-production is resource intensive and not incentivised (Nissan et al., 2019).
- v. **Responsibilities:** as an important part of the adaptation agenda, climate services should be just and address tractable problems equitably (Vaughan & Dessai, 2014). Climate service producers should be accountable for appropriate and accessible data, which requires ongoing funding. Initiatives such as CMIP provide accessibility but one consequence is the potential to exert a normalising effect which, for example, may discourage outlier solutions (Hourdin et al., 2023).

These data tensions arise from misalignments between modelling and the information needs of a range of sectoral users. The end of the report returns to these five issues to reflect on the current and future state of climate modelling, data and services. But first, some historical context.

2. A historic perspective on usable information

Since international and historical contexts are part of the use or misuse of data, the lead provided by the World Meteorological Organisation is significant. The WMO is the coordinating authority on the science and services of weather and climate, including standards, data exchange and collaboration. In the 2011 strategy and official guidelines in 2015 (WMO, 2015) the emphasis for weather forecasts became impact-based. The WMO wanted services to bridge the gap between predictions and potential consequences (Figure 2), 'a paradigm shift' in service delivery (WMO, 2015 p7).

It is no longer enough to provide a good weather forecast or warning – people are now demanding information about what to do to ensure their safety and protect their property.

Figure 2: WMO guidance on impact-based forecasts (WMO, 2015)

Climate services were developing at this time, often provided by the national meteorological services who comprise the WMO. Simultaneously, global programmes such as Future Earth encouraged 'usable science' to include the knowledge and values of stakeholders (Coen, 2021). The 2015 UN Sustainable Development Goals stressed interconnected issues. Climate service providers have, for over a decade, been self-consciously aware to be multidisciplinary and integrated with user needs.

To illustrate the awareness of user needs and effective communication has been a longstanding effort, here are reflections on conveying meteorological information from two perspectives, one current day looking back at climate research over the last 40 years and establishing decades of development to usable science through users (Coen, 2021) and one written on operational meteorology thirty years ago demonstrating the view on value in predictions (Murphy, 1993). Both papers make specific references on the limits of prediction.

2.1 Usable climate science

Deborah Coen proposes that usable science is not a new concept, it was established through the 20th century, but that even as climate institutions have embraced usability over the last 40 years they have clung to older and conflicting definitions of research where autonomy through a hierarchy of merit has been prized (Coen, 2021).

In the 19th century meteorology went from a wealthy gentleman's leisure activity, as described by John Ruskin, to establishment of the UK Met Office in 1854 and the first warning service in 1861. With the rise of state sponsored science in the 19th century there was a conflict between the demands of industry and the desired autonomy of the researcher and their purity for the 'love of truth'. In the 20th century the categories of 'applied' and 'industrial' science allowed some illusion of distancing between pursuit of pure science and its application, including in meteorology as the military shaped the research agenda. From the 1970s and 1980s onwards researchers and institutions reflected on their own practices of knowledge production, but those who pursued usable knowledge faced precarious careers. In meteorology, for example, credit and research funding tended to flow to work on models, not applications. Through institutes such as the Stockholm Environment Institute (1989), sustainability science was shaped, and stakeholder engagement became more central. However, usable knowledge is hyper-pragmatic and therefore 'its validity cannot be established by peer review, but only by the role it plays for a community of users'. In the context of usable science research is 'care for data and its analysis, and care for people and their relationships' and 'making science usable means institutionalising research as care'.

The Coen description of usable climate science has much in common with the current critiques of climate services discussed in section 3.3 and the challenges of section 5. Predictive modelling had limited value for climate science, even aside from the epistemic limits to the predictability of the climate system. For example, citizens and policymakers in poorer countries rarely have the luxury to plan decades out. Downscaling from GCMs may not increase useability without acknowledging limitations to predictive certainty at the local scale – discussed in section 5.3. Decisions about adaptive measures can often be made based on qualitative conclusions alone. Instead, the need is to foster legitimacy and trust through dialogue; to aim for an enhanced understanding of different evaluative criteria on the part of all role players.

2.2 Weather forecasts

A paper published in 1993 considered that a ‘good forecast’ consisted of the correspondence of the forecaster judgement and their forecast (consistency), the forecast matching observations (quality) and the benefits realised by a decisionmaker using the information (value) (Murphy, 1993) (Figure 3).

The author asserts that to ignore uncertainty when formulating and communicating forecasts represents an extreme form of inconsistency, which cause reductions in quality and value. There might, however, be trade-offs between consistency – or completeness – and conciseness in translating judgements into forecasts.

Figure 3: goodness in weather forecasting (Murphy, 1993)

On the subject of quality, the author notes that verification typically focuses on skill and accuracy, but that neglects the user’s decision-making needs. ‘Forecasts possess no intrinsic value. They acquire value through their ability to influence decisions’. Forecast value varies from problem to problem and user to user comprising:

- i) the courses of action available to the decisionmaker,
- ii) the payoff structure,
- iii) the quality of the information used for decisions in the absence of forecasts and
- iv) the quality of forecasts.

It is often assumed that increases in forecast accuracy necessarily imply increases in forecast value. Forecasts of high quality may be of little or no value to some users because of the nature of their problems and relatively high quality of their prior information.

Despite being thirty years old the paper agrees with much that is raised on the provision of climate services. The description of value predates the WMO ‘paradigm shift’ to impact-based forecasts (Figure 2). The Murphy concept of value is more subtle, agreeing in principle with Nissan et al., (section 3.3) and Coen (section 2.1) that coarse resolutions or qualitative assessments may be more useful than detailed analyses.

It is interesting to note the similarity between the ‘consistency – quality – value’ analysis (Figure 3) with that of the requirements for an ethical product of being defensible, including uncertainty, fit for decision-making and well-documented (Table 1).

3. Climate services

3.1 Evolution

In a world where past conditions are not indicative of the current or future conditions, climate services exist to serve society’s needs to advance understanding and dramatically improve our use of climate information (Hewitt et al., 2012). The UN Global Framework for Climate Services (GFCS) has five goals (Figure 4) including reducing climate vulnerability and mainstreaming the use of climate information in decisions. Along with eight principles, the Framework stresses climate information as a public good, providing information access for the benefit of all countries with the priority of capacity building in developing countries – noting that funding from development banks, UN agencies and the private sector would be needed. The initial priority areas were agriculture and food security, disaster risk reduction, health and water resources.

Figure 4: goals of the GFCS (Hewitt et al., 2012)

There is rapidly growing demand for services, a new era driven by the open data policies of many public agencies, technological advancements allowing affordable business models, greater coordination between private and public sectors, and the improved skill of forecasts raising user confidence (Brunet et al., 2022). Climate services are helping society to understand and manage climate variability and change (WMO, 2023). The GFCS and others stress the need for cross-sector collaborations to understand the demand, to effectively bridge the gap between sectoral and climate science, ensure co-production to meet user needs, communication and evaluation (WMO, 2023). The challenge is to find ways to bring information to the decision context. Trust and intelligibility are important since many of the uncertainties are subjective and the predictions may be unverifiable e.g., for rare events. What is needed is to build a chain of evidence, each link open to assessment.

3.2 Ethics

In providing a service, choices and value judgements are made on the analysis and the information to present. It is important to appreciate that science is part of society and is not value free (Pulkkinen et al., 2022). Social values are integral to research and developing an awareness of this is a first step.

Figure 5: climate services ethics (Adams et al., 2015)

Values need not compromise impartiality and evaluation of societal consequences of errors is a marker of good scientific practice (Pulkkinen et al., 2022). Climate information providers are in a position of trust (Adams et al., 2015) and, beyond basic awareness of values influencing individual or funder priorities, working within an ethical framework (Figure 5) is a practical bounding of responsibilities. The climate services product itself should be credible and defensible, include descriptions of uncertainty, be fit for purpose to inform decisions, and documented with metadata and version history (Adams et al., 2015).

3.3 Current critiques of climate services

Fully understanding and accommodating the user context, even with co-production, has been shown in the literature to be a significant challenge and this engagement remains least understood (Di Fant et al., 2024). Solutions include clarity on sharing, intellectual property and commercial use (Soares & Buontempo, 2019), the multi or transdisciplinary approach such as including social scientists and embracing an apprenticeship model, immersing technical information providers with users (Herrick & Vogel, 2022). An ethical framework and the best practice of co-production means considering user information needs but also their value systems and decision contexts (Parker & Lusk, 2019).

The intersection of climate services and the role of the data and therefore data producers is the subject of a paper led by Keiran Findlater, finding that whilst climate services promise better decision-making they mainly focus on delivering better data (Findlater et al., 2021). In addition to highlighting the need for user-driven climate services the work found that the norms and institutions of climate science can lead to tensions in climate service delivery with a focus on better data – organisations prioritising enhancing accuracy and reliability rather than ultimate use.

A comprehensive paper led by Hannah Nissan focuses on the needs of international development, detailing how climate projections and climate services fail to meet those needs, exploring how the failure arose, and how climate scientists can better serve this user group (Nissan et al., 2019). The primary themes to improve on the misuse of climate data are:

- *Projections* – instead of end of century global projections, the spatial and temporal timescales which are most suitable for development are shorter term, and include inter-annual or seasonal variability, and extremes. A longer-term trend may be contrary to the near-term leading to opportunity cost. Statistical downscaling is not a panacea for inadequate resolution and relies on past weather data which may not be available in low-income countries.
- *Confidence and uncertainty* – communicating confidence and the true range of uncertainty. Users have a false impression of confidence in climate change information by the illusion of precision. Models are not independent, so agreement does not increase confidence unless supported by scientific reasoning. For users, whilst limitations are often documented, they are often not set out for non-specialists. Under deep uncertainty then scenario planning is a pragmatic approach. Many in the field are willing to provide quick off the shelf answers. New ways are needed to assess confidence through expert judgement.
- *Resourcing* – the paper highlights that user engagement can be useful to truly streamline and tailor the information, to deliver the most effective outcomes for adaptation, which may not be the need for extensive quantitative climate projections. Detailed planning may be possible with coarse data or qualitative trends rather than detailed projections.

Finally, in the growing literature of business needs, including climate-related financial risk disclosure, a criticism voiced is that climate risk information is limited and expensive. A US study noted that ‘many providers of climate services use black box models that make overseeing the scientific rigour of their methods impossible... obfuscating the uncertainty in their projections’ (Condon, 2023) and some providers are ‘operating outside the bounds of scientific merit’ (Fiedler et al., 2021). An earlier study from Australia concluded that emphasising climate services shifts away from public interest to the pursuit of profit (Keele, 2019). A paper surveying Tiwanese businesses stressed the preference for physical risk information on the 5-to-10-year horizon and at fine spatial scales – highlighting inevitable data tensions. The same paper also called for better public guidance in understanding the data and the research from which it is derived (Lee et al., 2022). All echoed the GFCs stance of the public good in the knowledge required for society to respond to climate change.

4. Climate modelling challenges relevant to climate services

Climate modelling is used to determine how the climate might change in the future and is at the heart of climate science (McSweeney, 2022). Alongside observations, the robustness in understanding the climate system is based on complex numerical modelling. Global climate models are the basis for much of the work of the IPCC, fundamentally in the physical science of WG1, and as inputs to the impacts and adaptation of WG2 and informed by the emission pathways and iteration on mitigation with WG3 (Pirani et al., 2024). Climate models provide long-term predictions over large spatial scales, suitable for guiding mitigation plans and broad adaptation strategies (Nissan et al., 2019) but which need further processing to provide information suitable for the local needs of climate services and adaptations.

In this section the fundamental uncertainty in long-term predictions is outlined, along with the particular challenge of modelling and communicating extreme events. These modelling challenges present limitations to climate services, both in real terms in the expectation of future conditions and in the communication of the service and ultimate use. In the following section, section 5, such practicalities are illustrated with examples of data use in climate services from the literature, where service providers make important choices on data use and presentation in service creation. To continue with the practicalities, in section 6 decision support tools are discussed since they are common outputs of research projects and provide controlled ways for users to interact with data.

4.1 Uncertainty

In weather forecasting, which uses similar models to climate projections, skill is defined as the performance in comparison with a reference such as persistence or climatology. Given the timescales and changes over time, it is hard to assess predictions against actual outcomes for climate models, so modellers talk in terms of uncertainty in the models and predictions (Hargreaves, 2010). The spread of the Climate Model Intercomparison Projects (CMIPs) can be considered a guide to the uncertainty (Hargreaves, 2010) – although potentially insufficient (Hourdin et al., 2019). No matter how much the models are improved in their ability to reproduce past and present climates, it is possible that processes important for future climate change have been omitted (Hargreaves, 2010).

The future projections of climate models are the basis of the information contained in climate services and therefore fundamental. At a global level the uncertainty in climate predictions arises from three sources (Figure 6, Figure 7): natural internal climate variability (orange), model uncertainty (blue) and emission scenario uncertainty (green) (Hawkins & Sutton, 2009).

- i. *The internal climate variability* is the fluctuations in the absence of anthropogenic radiative forcing on time scales from days to decades or longer and include ENSO, MJO and changes in ocean currents; they could be more precisely quantified by not reduced (IPCC WG1, 2021 p197).
- ii. *Model uncertainty* is where different models simulate different changes in climate in response to the same radiative forcing (Hawkins & Sutton, 2009). Sources of uncertainty include parameterisations of sub-grid scale processes, model resolution, the implementation of numerical schemes and equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) – the long term change in surface temperature in response to a change in the atmospheric carbon dioxide (McSweeney, 2022).
- iii. *Emission scenario uncertainty* is the potential for differences in assumed future emissions of greenhouse gases. Concentration scenarios, derived from emission scenarios, are used as inputs to climate models (IPCC WG1 Annex VII, 2021). Climate model projections show that the uncertainties in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations at 2100 are dominated by the differences between emissions scenarios (high confidence) (IPCC WG1, 2021 p20).

Figure 6 plots the fraction of total variance by decade for each source of uncertainty for air temperature at the global and at an illustrative regional level (British Isles) based on CMIP3. The dashed lines indicate reductions in internal variability, and hence total uncertainty, that may be possible through initialisation by the assimilation of ocean observations (also a conclusion of Hawkins et al., 2015). Hawkins & Sutton similarly analysed for the sources of uncertainty in global and regional precipitation changes (Hawkins & Sutton, 2011) (Figure 7) and found that model uncertainty dominates at all timescales for global projections, >70% of the total variance, and for regional analysis internal variability was important initially and decreased over time.

More recent work (Lehner et al., 2020) has allowed a systematic characterisation of projection uncertainty by using seven of the CMIP6 members, comparable due to a consistent projection time period and the same emission scenarios. This work shows that for averages over large spatial scales the Hawkins and Sutton approach is reasonable.

Figure 6: relative sources of uncertainty, decadal temperature (Hawkins & Sutton, 2009)

Figure 7: relative sources of uncertainty, decadal precipitation (Hawkins & Sutton, 2011)

4.2 Extreme events

Whilst the previous section dealt with the long-term and large-scale, an important category in the deficiencies of climate modelling is their limited ability to capture extreme events. These high impacts outliers are of interest within many or all climate services and overlap with weather phenomena and socioeconomics – from increasing clear-air turbulence for aviation to storm surge flooding to record-breaking wildfires. These extremes may be rare in their increased intensity, duration, spatial scale, or frequency, or never previously seen. Extremes can produce severe impacts either acutely (e.g., storms, heatwaves) or chronically (e.g., droughts, ice-free seas) and any may have compounding or cascading effects (e.g., with concurrent meteorological events, society, ecology, or food systems).

To improve modelling predictions requires improving the factors controlling development (Sillman et al., 2017). The large-scale drivers include representing the weakening of the equator-pole temperature gradient, atmospheric blocking patterns, stratospheric-tropospheric connections and the jet stream position/intensity. Local to regional feedback and drivers include snow cover and sea surface temperature anomalies. Ways to progress modelling is by improving process theories, model resolution and novel sub-grid parameterisations, including land-atmosphere coupling and preconditioning for extreme events such as soil moisture. The Sillman paper stresses that ‘our ability to predict extremes will be hampered by making assumptions about linearity between processes’.

Given the high profile and high impacts of extreme events they are an important part of climate services, ethically to avoid harms a user most wants to avoid (Parker & Lusk, 2019) and practically to indicate worst cases (Blankespoor et al., 2023). Extreme events, along with event attribution, conflate the issues of weather, climate, and climate change both by the real underlying mechanisms such as preconditioning, and in societal awareness and responses and therefore climate service users. A recent paper on business risk notes extreme events ‘are the most challenging to assess and whether climate modelling yields useful information is currently being explored’ (Fiedler et al., 2021).

5. Examples of data challenges in climate services

Climate services involve the provision of climate information in such a way as to assist decision making (IPCC WG1 Annex VII, 2021). There are multiple challenges in the use of climate data, some can be avoided or alleviated by understanding user needs, but some are intertwined with the data and are discussed here. From an ethical point of view an inductive risk approach protects against the climate harms a user most wants to avoid, appreciating errors which would have particularly bad consequences from the user's perspective and prioritising avoidance of those errors in methods and presentation (Parker & Lusk, 2019). Such errors are unknown without having direct user consultation. There are also socio-political issues around climate change; not all communities are prioritising climate change and addressing it requires funding, expertise and time outside of existing budgets and capacity (Collini et al., 2021), information provided may not be used directly.

As a specific data challenge, many climate change effects occur on shorter timescales and more local spatial scales than grid-lengths or resolutions of global climate models. Internal climate variability and model uncertainty increases for smaller spatial scales and short projection time horizons (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 567) (Figure 6 shows global uncertainty on left and regional on the right for the British Isles). For regional precipitation changes the emission scenario uncertainty is often small relative to model response uncertainty (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 198).

Downscaling and bias correction often contribute substantial uncertainty to local decision-relevant climate metrics (Lafferty & Sriver, 2023) and neglecting to account for these uncertainties may risk overconfidence relative to the full range of climate futures. The results for temperature are shown for three selected cities from five different downscaling ensembles (Figure 8), the ensemble mean shown as the coloured line in the top row. The relative contributions to variance show that, for air temperature, the scenario becomes non-negligible after 2050 and the downscaling uncertainty declines but is substantial, especially for Lagos. The same paper investigates precipitation finding the scenario and model uncertainties small and downscaling and especially internal variability dominate.

Figure 8: downscaled air temperature for three cities (Lafferty & Sriver 2023)

Model updates, whilst beneficial for providing new information based on improved techniques, can also have the burden of potentially being the starting point for change. Facing changes in outputs can trigger resistance due to cognitive bias of anchoring on the existing (old) information, raising questions of how to respond, challenging the inertia of existing or legacy states.

Greater and greater certainty is a societal expectation from science and yet challenging. For example, on the topic of equilibrium climate sensitivity, but which could be applied to much of climate modelling 'it is sometimes assumed that parameterisation improvements will eventually lead to convergence in model response and therefore decrease in spread of ECS... despite decades of model development... there has been no systematic convergence... overall spread in ECS is larger in CMIP6 than CMIP5' (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 1008).

The following are three examples from the literature where climate services have faced challenges in the use of climate projection data. The examples are illustrative, chosen where it was possible to identify a data issue in recent papers. The first includes the issue of model selection from the ensemble members in CMIP5 or CMIP6 and the transparency of model choice, published by the data producer. The second is on well controlled uncertainty and deep uncertainty in sea level rise (SLR) and how users interact with SLR information. The third is published by the producer of a decision tool, an example of a climate service which has a clear audience and quantitative outputs, but potentially overstretches the credible use of projection data as an input for hydrological modelling and without providing uncertainty information.

5.1 Model selection & model families – *hot models in CMIP6*

A significant recent challenge for climate projections has been the high ECS and therefore higher levels of surface warming in a 'substantial subset' of models in the CMIP6 ensemble compared with CMIP5 (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 1008). This issue presents two data challenges for climate services, whether to use all CMIP models and on what basis to exclude models, and that the ECS itself as a potential example of the modelling community aligning too closely using families of models with interdependencies so there could be common limitations and biases (IPCC WG1, 2021 p 108) and underestimating spread.

To avoid extreme warming in the end of century projections, the solution in AR6 was to constrain the model results by observations (Hausfather et al., 2022). At the same time the ECS in AR6 was determined more certain, AR5 indicated a 66% chance that ECS was between 1.5 and 4.5C and AR6 concluded a 90% chance of between 2C and 5C (IPCC WG1 FAQs, 2021 p 44) with 3C as the best estimate (Hansen et al., 2023). Whilst some propose to exclude models with ECS above 5C from climate impact studies (Hausfather et al., 2022) other scientists disagree that this sole determinant is sufficient and point out that historical mean global warming is a poor constraint on future warming and that models should only be excluded if compromised by physical errors (Bloch-Johnson et al., 2022). Using observed climate trends over the last decades to constrain ECS may omit the multi-decadal internal climate variability contributing to recent climate trends (Hourdin et al., 2023). There is no direct relationship between ECS and 20th century warming, given the uncertainty of aerosol forcing and the 'pattern effect' of SST spatial patterns evolving over time (Hourdin et al., 2023).

Recent work led by James Hansen indicated that the IPCC has underestimated ECS, analysing our historical climate change cannot define ECS well and a higher ECS leads to longer lead times to fully reach equilibrium and therefore there is much more 'global warming in the pipeline' (Hansen et al., 2023). Machine Learning work on decomposing model tuning to explore the ECS also concluded that it may be underestimated by CMIP exercises (Hourdin et al., 2023). To complicate matters further

with observational data, in the paper ‘climate models can’t explain 2023’s huge heat anomaly’ Gavin Schmidt, quantifies the influences of ENSO, lower shipping emissions and the Tonga volcanic eruption, still leaving a gap of 0.2C. He concludes that there is ‘an unprecedented knowledge gap’ implying that warming has altered how the climate system operates or statistical inferences based on past events are less reliable than previously thought (Schmidt, 2024). Gavin Schmidt is a co-author on the Hausfather paper. Hausfather recently restated that ‘there is still reason to doubt very high climate sensitivity models’ and our best estimate remains somewhere between 2C and 5C (Hausfather & Dessler, 2024).

The hot model issue presents choices for any presentation of CMIP6 data, including where that data is downscaled for local use for climate services or decision support tools or visualisations. The issue exemplifies the statistical analysis and plethora of data which have to be produced to maintain transparency and traceability. The Canadian Climate Change Service presents downscaled data on a platform for open use to visualise or manipulate with Jupyter notebooks, and published a study (Cannon, 2024) on whether the globally constrained CMIP6 projections for Canada were appreciably different from unconstrained projections. The CMIP6 ensemble of models were constrained by excluding those with a high ECS or weighting to achieve similar – noting the loss of information that this might cause. Using the unconstrained ensemble, by the end of century the mean warming in northern Canada is 2-3C warmer and 20 to 40% wetter than the constrained methods. As an alternative, which is consistent with the IPCC approach e.g., in the Interactive Atlas, is to present projections at a specified level of warming, with the timing of the warming level exceedance constrained. The work recommends that results from the CMIP6 ensemble be accompanied by statements of impacts of the hot model problem on regional projections.

The ECS issue is and has been the subject of ongoing research, but the resulting hot models of CMIP6 have cast a spotlight on the impacts of large potential biases due to consensus – something which sea level rise had already had to deal with – discussed next.

5.2 Deep uncertainty & user knowledge – sea level rise

Sea level rise (SLR) presents both a steady and predictable impact, measured to be increasing at 1.3 ± 0.2 mm/year (NASA, 2024), but with the potential for large ice sheet contributions from accelerations or tipping points leading to catastrophically higher values but with deep uncertainty. The emphasis of overreliance on consensus in AR4 led to alternatives to model-based approaches such as empirical analysis and expert elicitation (Oppenheimer et al., 2007) and low-likelihood, high-impact scenarios are now included in AR6 (Figure 9).

The climate services for SLR continue to highlight problems for users of the information. Two papers from 2023, with authors in common, examined difficulties of using SLR projections for planning and adaptation. The first surveyed planner use of projections and found that of 250 practitioners, only 72% used projection data. There was an overreliance on singular estimates and inconsistent approaches on the selection of projections (Hirschfeld et al., 2023). The authors concluded a disconnect between science and planning which raises concerns of coastal managers’ ability to translate uncertain futures into adaptation decisions, especially for high-end increases.

The second focused on the needs of local planning and how that can be better served by SLR research (Blankespoor et al., 2023). The paper had several suggestions including the need for accessible and easily used data (not just research formats), that global SLR studies have indirect influence by raising awareness but cannot inform directly as they lack local information and that

planners are less keen on probability distributions and ask for a most likely and a worst-case scenario, or a range driven by emission scenarios.

There were several common conclusions. Firstly, that different people make different choices using the same information, which does not mean a misunderstanding of the science but rather a diversity of risk tolerance. Another was on national specifics such as countries with histories of adaptation and consistent national support show greater assimilation of SLR projections into adaptation decisions. The survey paper noted that some planners may not consult SLR data because they are compelled by guidance to do otherwise, and scenarios should be politically appropriate for the location. An informative conclusion and framing in the Blankespoor paper was that as long as credibility, salience and legitimacy of information are all high enough then global datasets can inform decisions.

A third paper from 2023, on communicating SLR uncertainty (Kopp et al., 2023) also notes that there is a quantifiable and well defined distribution for SLR but also ambiguity or deep uncertainty where there is unknown or disagreement on i) models to describe interactions in system variables, ii) the probability distributions of uncertainty and/or iii) how to value the desirability of outcomes. AR6 includes projections above the 'likely' range for stakeholders with a low risk tolerance. This low confidence projections were presented alongside the suite of SSP scenarios of medium confidence. AR6 also includes low-likelihood, high-impact with a plot to

2300 to show that SLR of >15m cannot be ruled out with high emissions (Figure 9).

Figure 9: SLR AR6

5.3 Model resolution & uncertainty – temperature & flood predictions

A climate service which has a clear audience and quantitative outputs is described in Tikul et al., 2022, but the account of the method appears to overstretch the credible use of projection data as an input for hydrological modelling and without providing uncertainty information. Downscaling, discussed earlier, can have significant impacts on the output uncertainty. Decomposing the downscaling contribution to uncertainty would require expertise on the physical processes affecting a location's climate, the location representation in the global climate model(s) and how outputs are affected by the downscaling method (Lafferty and Sriver, 2023).

The study developed a web-based climate service to allow building owners and designers to reduce the impacts of climate change (Tikul et al., 2022). The impact information provided included highest annual surface temperature, maximum flood level, flood duration and water velocity displayed on maps each future year out to 2047. The website also contained guidance on recommendations for climate-resilient design, including a database of 46 options on building materials. The tool was produced to help building experts work with climate data using an easy interface because 'climate information in the literature can differ considerably, confusing designers'.

The multidisciplinary work used the output of two global models, from the Max Planck Institute and the Hadley Centre, under a total of eight scenarios – using four grid points. The points were statistically downscaled to a 25 x 25km grid (Figure 10), combined with land-use, topography and a hydrological model. The quality of each global model was assessed by historic observations of one day maximum temperature and one day maximum precipitation for one weather station from 1980 to 2017. Linear regression analysis was used to fit the past and predict the future. Landsat data

from 1998 to 2017 were calibrated on the weather station data and used to produce temperature maps of 30 x 30 metres. For flooding, the one-day maximum precipitation for each of the eight scenarios was used with catchment and river dimensions to calculate peak discharge and compared with five water quantity stations in the study area. Inundation maps were created.

Figure 10: area of interest (Tikul et al., 2022)

The work provided a practical tool tailored for a clear end user group with additional adaptation options and information in the same place as climate information. The potential downsides are in the use of the projection data. The paper did not explicitly mention uncertainty nor how reliance on one observational site for extreme temperature and precipitation might lead to bias. Calibrating on a single site historic relationship may not be valid in the future regime of a warmer world. Nor did the paper mention that it might be a stretch on the model resolution to use four grid points as the basis for extensive hydrological modelling for three rivers, which includes precise outputs on flood duration, flood height and water velocity. There are numerous papers on the difficulties of and differences in predicting rainfall and the extremes, for example Lopez-Cantu et al., 2020.

As an example from the paper, temperature series were presented in the tool and paper by individual year with no error bars (Figure 11), here the tool highlights that 2044 is the hottest year. Best practice is to provide period averages (for example Figure 12).

Figure 11: temperature series presented in Tikul et al., 2022

6. Data application: decision support tools

Having discussed categories of data challenges, here the service itself will be considered, including the use of data, guided by the ethical framework for products introduced in section 3.2. The climate services product should be credible and defensible, include descriptions of uncertainty, be fit for purpose to inform decisions, and documented with metadata and version history (Adams et al., 2015) (Table 1).

Table 1: ethical components of a climate service product (after Adams et al., 2015)

<i>CREDIBLE & DEFENSIBLE</i>	<i>INCLUDE UNCERTAINTY</i>	<i>INFORM DECISIONS</i>	<i>WELL DOCUMENTED</i>

It has become common for research organisations to generate products and tools that support informed decisions making for increased social and environmental resilience (Collini et al., 2021). An example of a global and regional scale visualisation of climate data is the Interactive Atlas of WG1 of the IPCC (IPCC AR6-WG1, 2021), a novel contribution to the sixth assessment with a range of variables so that users can interrogate, map and average over a range of scenarios and timescales. The Atlas is absolutely defensible since it is a product of and consistent with the IPCC WG1 report, uncertainty is included by, for example, including hatchings where models disagree and documented under FAIR data principles (Iturbide et al., 2022). The Atlas is presented as a visualisation and explorer rather than a decision support tool, so it makes no claim suggesting which decisions it will inform. Earlier this year the Copernicus Climate Change Service launched a new version which operationalises the Atlas providing up to date data rather than the ‘frozen’ AR6 of the IPCC – becoming its ‘live evolution’ (ECMWF, 2024).

There are also tailored post-processed decision support tools which focus on a region and specific variables of interest to certain users. A recent paper reviewed twenty decision support tools from the US (Jahan et al., 2023). The authors concluded that the tools are quite thorough on presenting detailed climate information and including explanatory material, but few discuss the specific decisions they will support or the role that climate can play, they are potentially therefore not fit for purpose to inform decisions.

Whilst it is common to find papers published on new tools as they are launched which describe the co-development with users and features of the outputs, few projects return to publish evaluations years later. An exception was a paper on understanding an online climate resilience tool, Gulf TREE, which garnered 52 survey responses after more than a year from launch (Collini et al., 2021). The stakeholder engagement during development had been good, with positive evaluations prior to release. In beta-testing workshops, 89% indicated intention to continue using the tool but only 44% of the respondents who had participated in that beta-testing had subsequently used the tool. The authors conclude that usability, even with intention to adopt, is not a good proxy for adoption.

Next is the description of one such project, chosen from the literature to illustrate the genre with a clear user group, vigneron. This case highlights the conflation of shorter-term predictions, seasonal forecasts, presented alongside climate projections, but is otherwise a well-presented service.

6.1 Wine production in Australia

A recent example of a decision support tool has been developed in Australia by the government research establishment, CSIRO, and the national weather service, the Bureau of Meteorology. They have produced the Climate Service for Agriculture platform to provide data and climate projections relevant to agricultural commodities. A paper details the functionality using wine production as the example (Webb et al., 2023) noting that wine producers are already thinking about a longer-term time horizon. The platform has historical data and future projections in one place, on a 5km grid, and seasonal outlooks only for rainfall. The Rutherglen region is included as a worked example and shows how recorded long-term averages (top, Figure 12) compare with projections (bottom, Figure 12), with uncertainty ranges included.

Figure 12: screen shot of CSA platform showing past and future temperature

Table 2: summary of platform ethically consistent features (taken from Webb et al., 2023)

	<p>CMIP5 data were used with RCP8.5 and RCP4.5 Historic and seasonal data were provided by the national weather service – which is routinely produced. Growing degree days, mean growing season temperature, extreme heat index, frost index, rainfall indices.</p>
	<p>‘Uncertainties at regional and local scales over the next decade are strongly influenced by natural variability, which is hard to predict.’ ‘Users of the climate data should acknowledge the uncertainties and limitations ... and consider how these might affect their conclusions and confidence’ ‘Full uncertainty in future climate conditions are not reflected as there may be local effects...’ A number of other factors will influence the outcome from shifts in climate including adaptation practices, soil moisture, timing and intensity of rainfall, varietal differences.</p>
	<p>‘User engagement has directly influenced the development’ ‘The goal is shifting from a focus on improving access to information to improve how the information is used’ The information presented is aimed as being relevant for wine production.</p>
	<p>Data provenance: historical data and seasonal forecast data from the Bureau of Meteorology. Rainfall and temperature projections for 2030, 2050 and 2070 from CSIRO and the Bureau https://www.climatechangeinaustralia.gov.au/</p>

7. Reflections & future

As introduced at the beginning of this report, there are five interwoven considerations on climate data and how it might be practically and appropriately incorporated into a usable service which avoids the misuse of data. All five appear in the literature as sources of the misalignment between climate data and the information needs of a range of sectoral users. This section reflects on the body of knowledge explored in this report and adds thoughts on future data, services and requirements.

i. *Purpose*

Climate models are research tools to inform mitigation and to investigate and refine the Earth-system processes relevant to the carbon cycle. Climate models are similar to weather forecasting models and often are produced by national weather services. There are two developments at the intersection of weather and climate modelling.

Firstly the call for a ‘CERN for climate change’ (Palmer, 2024), the most vocal being Tim Palmer who pioneered ensemble modelling methods for medium range weather forecasts. Starting in 2011, and even commenting this month in reaction to the high and unexplained temperature of 2023, he is calling for pooling international resources to achieve 1km spatial grids in global climate models. Similarly there have been calls to operationalise climate models (Jakob et al., 2023) for continuity of funding and to separate pure research from servicing users – perhaps preserving the autonomy through a hierarchy of merit described by Deborah Coen (section 2.1, Coen, 2021). As a counter argument, the slow improvement of climate models has raised questions whether coarse resolution global circulation models with parameterized physics have become obsolete (Hourdin et al., 2023) and even global cloud resolving models will still need parameterisations of microphysics and other processes.

Secondly there is much effort into consolidating a seamless prediction chain, from weather to climate projections, known as NEWP in a recent WMO white paper (Brunet, 2022). Driven by weather and climate risk-based decision-making, needs of just in time supply chains, and needs for enhanced resilience. The seamless presentation of these datasets for different lead times may raise interpretation issues due to the changes in uncertainty and how that is communicated.

ii. *Accuracy*

There are climate modellers who are increasingly vocal on using climate models as tools complementing expert judgement and not being too focused on model development (Stainforth, 2020; Thompson, 2023) and model evaluation should be less about reducing uncertainty about the future but instead improving confidence levels (Nissan et al., 2019). However, the norms of climate science may lead providers to continue to focus on better data (Findlater et al., 2021) and modelling as a scientific endeavour continues to extend and improve model representations and quantify and reduce uncertainties.

In addition to improvements in numerical schemes and model physics, deconstructing the CMIP members is being proposed to explore model uncertainty. For example, for models participating in CMIPs, each centre goes through ‘model tuning’ for their contributions to the IPCC, a stage which may omit uncertainty and results in a single best guess model. Machine learning or emulators can be used to systematically explore the range of tuning components within each model, using numerous short simulations to extract a small subset of acceptable configurations, although this approach would neglect long duration ocean effects (Hourdin et al., 2023). Another

approach is to more formally use the members of CMIP to explore model uncertainty, moving from the ensemble of opportunity or collection of best guesses, and, for example, interchangeably plugging together component parts of the different models to explore the response (Jebeile & Crucifix, 2020).

As time passes there will be more opportunity for verification over the long durations necessitated by climate change timescales. The performance of historic climate models have been analysed for their ability to project future global mean surface temperature changes. The models showed warming consistent with observations when mismatches between model projected and observationally estimated forcings were considered (Hausfather et al., 2019).

The hot model problem and continuing scientific dialogue over equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) is a good example of how striving for fundamental understanding in climate science has a direct impact on climate service products. Furthermore, the issue of model selection and the debate on whether models are too conformist illustrates the importance of expert judgement in what might otherwise be considered objective modelling. Taking a clear impact viewpoint, Zeke Hausfather, who has been vocal on maintaining the validity of the normalising approach used by the IPCC, stresses that ‘Ongoing research will continue to sharpen our understanding of ECS but it won’t change the immediate task before us: the rapid decarbonisation of our society. This remains our paramount challenge, regardless of the precise severity of the climate threat.’ (Hausfather & Dessler, 2024).

iii. *Impacts*

From an ethical point of view an inductive risk approach should protect against the climate harms a user most wants to avoid (Parker & Lusk, 2019). In answering the question of ‘do projections underestimate or overestimate impacts?’ requires at least a plausible worst case to be mentioned in climate services, but not excessively as this may waste money and become an opportunity cost (Nissan et al., 2019).

There are many circumstances which could lead to underestimates of climate change impacts. Climate models in CMIP are not independent and therefore may be insufficiently spread (Hourdin et al., 2019). Outlier models and their results should be taken more seriously, model runs should be preregistered to reduce outlier rejections, and alternative modelling approaches should be considered than the current computing norms (Thompson, 2023). Ultra-high resolution models might encourage planning for highly specific scenarios (Stainforth, 2023). The climate or society may pass tipping points which are not included in climate models (Rising et al., 2022).

Under such deep uncertainties that climate change presents, then scenario planning is a pragmatic approach (Nissan et al., 2019). This more narrative style has been presented in the literature, including by the IPCC, as ‘storylines’ approach. Unprecedented events are a special challenge for weather and climate services, but can be approached with storylines which takes the weather event as a given and explores the effects of known aspects of climate change such as higher sea surface temperatures (WMO, 2021 p26-27). Physical climate storylines are a physically self-consistent unfolding of past events or plausible future events or pathways where no prior probability is assessed (Baulenas et al., 2023).

The criticism of RCP8.5 as an unrealistically high emissions scenario would lead to overpredictions, but there is much in emission scenarios – created using Integrated Assessment

Models, which fundamentally influence long-term climate projections. A detailed examination of IAMs is beyond the scope of this report but have two important effects on projections. Firstly, as described in 'the missing risks of climate change' (Rising et al., 2022) they lag climate science, hide variability, and do not translate biophysical risks into economic ones. IAMs are performative and can provide a conviction narrative whereby their existence and predictions change the future, but the models themselves do not have mechanisms to include such behaviour (Thompson, 2023). Secondly, IAMs are cost optimised and therefore required to evaluate everything into dollars which results in self-fulfilling technology based solutions rather than aiming for outcomes based on societal values or needs (Thompson, 2023).

iv. *Users*

Here there is a balance to find, providing enough credible information for users in a convenient format, including uncertainty statements but not overloading, and providers understanding that users may not use the information.

Data visualisations and decision support tools are increasingly being developed as part of research projects, including the Interactive Atlas (IPCC AR6-WG1, 2021). Many tools adhere to the ethical components required of a climate services product, being credible and defensible, include descriptions of uncertainty and documented, but they may fail to discuss the decisions they will support (Jahan et al., 2023). Organisations such as the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) have a wide range of visualisations and APIs for direct open-source data exchange which is creating new business models (Brunet et al., 2022), similarly the IPCC datasets have been made available under clear FAIR data standards. However there remains the risk that data will be poorly used e.g., Figure 11 and 'many in the field are willing to provide quick off the shelf answers' and 'numbers may be easily generated by models, but their reliability cannot be assumed' (Nissan et al., 2019).

The benefits of coproduction for user-centric information is a goal of climate services. Understanding the format and level of detail that a user is used to and can use may feel incomplete but be pragmatic and ultimately effective, for example planners are less keen on probability distributions and ask for a most likely and a worst case scenario (Blankespoor et al., 2023).

Predictions which are more accurate, with substantial efforts in reducing uncertainty by improving model formulations and inputs, may still be of no or low value to some users due to their own constraints or knowledge (Murphy, 1993). Not all communities are prioritising climate change (Collini et al., 2021) or other pressures are much more important, for example for flooding along parts of the West Africa coast, the growing population, coastward migration, urbanisation and unregulated socioeconomic developments will create greater exposure than sea level rise (Dada et al., 2023). An overall efficiency of user engagement could be to reduce the burden of full analysis and instead use targeted actionable information (Nissan et al., 2019) or qualitative conclusions may suffice (Coen, 2021).

In describing climate services and resulting adaptation actions some studies (e.g., Blankespoor et al., 2023) note that the point of traction to bring action on adaptation was the years after a significant event such as Hurricane Katrina directly reduced the risk tolerance of the Dutch to sea level rise. Therefore, timing may be part of successful user engagement, where a user perceives value in being prepared and informed by a climate service when boosted by the availability heuristic for a period after an extreme event. Event based storylines have been suggested as a

way to investigate and plausibly elaborate on extreme events with relevant user groups for stress testing on preparedness (Sillman et al., 2021).

v. *Responsibilities:*

Pure science, even model outputs, do not tell you what to do. Model projections were originally for the scientific understanding of the global climate system and to provide evidence for the need for greenhouse gas mitigation (Nissan et al., 2019). However, there are value judgements and ethics in producing models and their projections, and the resulting climate services, like weather forecasts, can influence decisions (Murphy, 1993).

Climate services are intended to reduce societal vulnerability to climate hazards, mainstream climate information in decision-making and strengthen the engagement of providers and users (Hewitt et al., 2012). The evaluation on the success of supporting equity is difficult to assess from the literature beyond the climate services provided for developing nations (e.g., Dada et al., 2023) and the open source visualisations and decision support tools, which although may be global and lack essential local detail, may still have indirect influence by raising awareness (Blankespoor et al., 2023).

Continuity of funding and coordination of science are motivations for establishing a ‘CERN for climate change’ (Palmer, 2024). This solution is in part refuted by some climate modellers (e.g., Nissan et al., 2019, Stainforth, 2020; Thompson, 2023;) with physically consistent storylines proposed as a richer description which is not objectively based on probability and making expert judgement more prominent than data. These initiatives would undoubtedly have repercussions for the funding and business models for national weather services and climate research centres and the climate services they develop.

Finally, there is a need to separate the facts and the values (Thompson, 2023). Projections are only one small part of creating awareness and presenting potential options. Similarly last year climate scientist Mike Hulme published a book called ‘Climate Change Isn’t Everything’ to stress the roles of beliefs, values and meaning and that there are numerous societal needs and systemic problems that require urgent attention besides future climate impacts (Hulme, 2023).

9300 words

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